

NOTES

A Method of Preparation of Solid Solutions of Calcium and Manganese (or Copper) Hydroxylapatite

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SOLID solutions of calcium and some divalent cations such as lead, strontium, etc., hydroxylapatites were prepared earlier¹ by firing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium and divalent cation hydroxylapatite at about 1570 K. These samples prepared by the solid state reaction were however found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous. The present work has been an attempt to arrive at a new method of preparation of the homogeneous solid solutions over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation.

Experimental

The chemicals used for the preparation of these samples were either AR (BDH) or E-MERCK extra pure grade. Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Solution A) and solution containing Mn²⁺ (or Cu²⁺) and Ca²⁺ ions in the proportion desired for the solid solutions (Solution B) were prepared separately in carbon dioxide free doubly distilled water and pH of these solutions were scrupulously maintained above 11 by the addition of excess of liquor ammonia. Then a part of the solution B was taken in a ZL flask with a side tube fitted with a three-hole rubber stopper carrying two separating funnels through two holes and a delivery tube through the third hole. Solution A and

Solution B were taken separately in the separating funnels and were allowed to drop into the flask while it was kept at 310±0.5 K. The precipitation was carried out in carbon dioxide free atmosphere and the medium of precipitation was well stirred by bubbling carbon dioxide free air into the medium of precipitation through the delivery tube. The precipitate along with the mother liquor was aged by boiling under reflux for 30 minutes to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate. The constancy of the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of calcium deficient apatites². The precipitate was washed thoroughly with doubly distilled water till it was free from ammonium salts. Samples dried at 373 K for few hours were analysed complexometrically³ and their molar volumes were determined by density method using toluene as the media⁴. The X-Ray diffraction patterns of powdered samples were obtained with a Norelco powder diffractometer employing Cu K_α radiation with a graphite monochromator. Sharp peaks separated by less than 0.1 degree (2θ) can be resolved with a 0.15 mm entrance slit at a scanning rate of 1 degree (2θ) per minute using tube voltage and current of 50KV and 20 mA respectively. The d-spacings and the corresponding a and c parameters values were calculated by the well known method of Azaroff⁵ and from them unit cell volumes of samples were calculated (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The results and chemical analysis and molar volume of the samples are given in Table 1. The molecular formulae of each of the samples was assigned on the basis of the results of chemical

TABLE 1(a)—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, MANGANESE HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Wt. %			Molecular formula	G. atom ratio Ca + Mn	Lattice parameters (Å)		
	Ca	Mn	P			a	c	Unit cell volume (Å ³)
1.	39.80	—	18.61	Ca ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67	9.97	6.88	522.9
2.	31.88	9.44	18.08	Ca _{9.2} Mn _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68	9.03	6.74	482.5
3.	22.76	20.88	17.64	Ca _{4.0} Mn _{6.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67	8.71	6.62	441.0
4.	14.62	30.17	17.00	Ca _{6.0} Mn _{4.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67	8.43	6.45	408.0
5.	6.77	39.66	16.58	Ca _{1.0} Mn _{9.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68	8.11	6.40	370.0
6.	—	47.55	16.64	Mn ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68	7.84	6.38	345.1

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TABLE 1(b)—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COPPER HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample no.	Wt%			Molecular formula	Molar volume ml	G. atom ratio Ca+Cu P	Lattice parameter		Unit cell volume
	Ca	Cu	P				a	c	
1.	39.80	—	18.61	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.60	1.68	9.37	6.38	522.3
2.	27.39	16.06	17.41	$\text{Ca}_{7.2}\text{Cu}_{2.7}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	347.26	1.67	9.26	6.81	507.2
3.	21.48	23.66	16.89	$\text{Ca}_{6.9}\text{Cu}_{4.1}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	354.83	1.67	9.14	6.74	489.8
4.	14.76	32.30	16.30	$\text{Ca}_{4.2}\text{Cu}_{5.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	352.78	1.67	9.03	6.68	474.0
5.	6.02	43.52	15.53	$\text{Ca}_{1.9}\text{Cu}_{8.1}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	350.98	1.67	8.92	6.60	467.7
6	—	51.25	15.00	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	347.68	1.67	8.83	6.53	443.0

analyses. The observed value of molar g atomic rates of $\frac{\text{Ca}}{\text{P}}$, $\frac{\text{M}}{\text{P}}$ for the end members and $\frac{\text{Ca}+\text{M}}{\text{P}}$, where $\text{M}=\text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Mn^{2+} were found to be equal to 1.67 (theoretical 1.67) was to indicate the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁵. The substitution of Ca^{2+} by Mn^{2+} (or Cu^{2+}) contract the unit cell of the apatites which confirm the formation of the solid solutions. Such a contraction with the proportion of MnHA (or CuHA) was evident from the excellent regularity with which the unit cell volume of the samples calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constants decreased with the proportion of MnHA or CuHA.

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Study on N,N'-Ethylenebis(Salicylaldiminato) Beryllium(II)†

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GREEN and Alexander¹ reported the formation of a hydrated beryllium complex with 'Salen' and assigned a formula $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Batley and Graddon² studied a number of beryllium

complexes of quadridentate Schiff bases derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde and ethylenediamine, 1, 3-trimethylenediamine and diamines containing four or six methylene groups in the amine bridge. These authors assigned hydrogen bonded structure and a formula, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{33}\text{BeN}_4\text{O}_{10}$ to the beryllium-salen complex. Singh and Kumar³ used 'Salen' as a gravimetric reagent for beryllium and assigned a possible formula, $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, to the weighable form of the precipitate. No elemental analysis was, however, reported by them for the hydrated precipitate. In the present paper, we are presenting the preparation of anhydrous beryllium-salen complex along with its ir, pmr, reflectance, mass spectral and TGA data for the first time. Based on these data a polymeric structure can be attributed to the complex.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 221. The pmr spectra were recorded on Varian Associates, Model T-60, operating at 60 Mc/s with TMS as an internal standard. Reflectance spectrum was recorded on a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer using MgCO_3 as standard. Mass spectra were recorded on CEC 21-110B (USA) double focussing mass spectrometer at a voltage 70 eV. TGA and DTA were carried out in a MOM Budapest derivatograph at the heating rate of 10°/min in flowing air atmosphere.

N, N'-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) was prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde and ethylenediamine in ethanol. The yellow shining product was purified by repeated recrystallisation.

Beryllium complex was prepared by reacting an acid solution of 'salen' [(2.68 g, 0.01 mole, dissolved in a few ml of acetic acid (~5 ml), 25 ml alcohol and diluting with water to ~125 ml)] with an aqueous solution of beryllium sulphate or nitrate (0.01 mole) dissolved in 10-20 ml water. The pH of the clear, yellow solution was adjusted to ~7 with dropwise addition of dilute ammonia (1:1). The yellow voluminous precipitate was converted into a crystalline easily filterable precipitate by digesting it on water bath for about an hour. The precipitate was

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